

Multi-Purpose Agriculture Robot

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Abstract— *This paper introducing a multi-purpose agriculture robot. At its core is a sophisticated weed plucking system using precision-driven linear actuators, minimizing damage to crops while removing invasive weed species. The robot employs real-time image processing techniques, powered by machine learning algorithms, to identify and eradicate weeds efficiently. Additionally, the robot features a state-of-the-art seed sowing system, ensuring precision and uniformity in seed distribution. Using pneumatic and electromagnetic mechanisms, it adapts seamlessly to varying soil types and topographies, optimizing seed placement for improved germination rates and crop yield. Beyond weed plucking and seed sowing, the robot integrates a comprehensive irrigation and pest management suite. A dynamic hog and sprinkler system deliver moisture control and pesticide application tailored to each crop's needs. Real-time data analytics and predictive modeling optimize irrigation and pesticide dosing, reducing water wastage and environmental impact while maximizing agricultural output.*

Keywords— *Seed Sowing, IOT, Linear Actuator ,Weed Removal*

INTRODUCTION.

A. Overview of the Internet of Things

The major idea of IoT is to endow with the network infrastructure through interoperable communication protocols and the software for a better data collection with a suitable connection, exchange of information through the nodes on several heterogeneous networks. Applications of IoT include, home automation systems of smart lighting, healthcare, pollution monitoring, and smart grid. Inappropriately, many connecting of devices to the Internet presents causes a more possible for cybercrime. Analyst Gartner estimates that in 2025 the IoT devices will be used by 64 billion, except tablets, PCs, and smartphones. Individuals and some companies using IoT devices cross the legal agreement. A smart refrigerator was hacked two years ago wherein it sends indecent spam by building the ice cubes. Baby alarms were used for eavesdropping on and still used to converse to the sleeping children. In the year 2016, the ever-largest Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack in opposition to Dyn, a provider of significant Domain Name System (DNS) services to companies like Netflix, Twitter, and CNN was done by hacking thousands of security cameras. And again, in the year 2017, Wikileaks divulge that Central Intelligence Agency.

B. Multi-purpose agriculture robot using IOT

idea of applying robotics technology in agriculture is very new. In agriculture, the opportunities for robot-enhanced productivity are immense - and the robots are appearing on farms in various guises and in increasing numbers. We can expect the robots performing agricultural operations autonomously such as ploughing, seed sowing, mud closing and water spraying. Watching the farms day and night for an effective report, allowing farmers to reduce the environmental impact, increase precision and efficiency, and manage individual plants in novel ways. The applications of instrumental robotics are spreading every day to cover further domains, as the opportunity of replacing human operators provides effective solutions with return on investment. This is specially important when the duties, that need be performed, are potentially harmful for the safety or the health of the workers, or when more conservative issues are granted by robotics. Heavy chemicals or drugs dispensers, manure or fertilizers spreaders, etc. are activities more and more concerned by the deployment of unmanned options.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Block diagram of model

LITERATURE SURVEY

Mr. Sridhar Kawadkar et.al [1], studied This seed plantation machine has great potential for increasing the productivity of the planting. Till now tractor was the main traction unit for nourishment in farming. With the adaptation of this seed planting machine its purpose will be done

Shreyash Pradip Patil et.al [2], This project plans to design fully functional automated product. In this proposed work, solar powered seed sowing and fertilizer spraying robot with wireless control will be successfully developed and implemented in real time environment. The proposed system will be developed at low power and low cost with an efficient output

Mahajan Vasudha et.al [3], Thus the “Automated sprinkler irrigation system based on soil moisture using Arduino” has been designed and tested successfully. It has been developed by different features of all the hardware components used. It is showing a pin diagram of the project. Thus, the Arduino Based Automatic sprinkler irrigation System has been designed and tested successfully Function of the system has been automatic.

S.Mathivanan et.al [4], Thus, we have come up with a low-cost Plant Irrigation Water Sprinkler Robot. The project carried out by us made an impressing task in the field of Agricultural industries. It is very useful for water irrigation from streams or rivers. This project has also reduced the cost involved in the concern. Project has been designed to perform the entire requirement task, which has also been provided.

Monis Akhtar et.al [5], This paper for selecting target 2D coordinate points in the pixel coordinate system, as well as the related traversal search box. To achieve real-time target for removal of weed

K.R. Gokul anand et.al [6], This project is proposed for reduce the human works on Agriculture sector and increase the flexibility in agriculture. It also exhibits a tiny step towards automation in Agriculture across the world. We can use this project in rough terrains without any suspensions with the help of Rocker bogie mechanism and we can trim the weeds at different height with the rack and pinion mechanism .

Anusha AC et.al [7], machine vision with appropriate image processing with the help of IoT-based intelligent robots is a promising means for precise and accurate means of weed detection and elimination in the field. This model or robot is also beneficial with reference to the selective herbicide, which drastically decreases the use of herbicide in the field, helping reduce many health problems.

Mekhala et.al [8] Internet of things (IoT) based intelligent robots is one of the most researched problems in recent times. Also, traditional methods for weed elimination by the use of herbicides have not been successful due to the acute toxicity of these herbicides, which leads to many health-related problems. Many approaches have been proposed to solve the problem statement. This paper presents various models and methods in the direction toward fast and accurate weed detection. In this paper, we also presented an IoT-based intelligent robot that will perform the task to weed detection and elimination remotely

I. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Deployment of Agricultural Robot: Deploy the multi-purpose agricultural robot equipped with its various functionalities:

Weed Removal: The robot features a weed removal mechanism driven by precision linear actuators. Ensure that the weed removal mechanism is calibrated and programmed to target and remove weed plants while minimizing damage to surrounding crops.

Seed Sowing: Integrate a seed sowing system into the robot, where a hog is used to drill holes in the soil for seed placement. Ensure the seed sowing system is capable of precise and uniform distribution of seeds across the field.

Irrigation: Incorporate an irrigation system into the robot to provide water to the crops. The irrigation system should be able to adjust water delivery based on soil moisture levels measured by IoT sensors.

Experimental Design: Design the experimental layout, dividing the field into distinct treatment zones or plots. Randomize the allocation of treatments to minimize bias and ensure statistical validity. Consider including control plots where traditional farming methods are employed for comparison.

Weed Removal Experiment: Conduct experiments to evaluate the robot's weed removal capabilities. Identify weed-infested areas within the field and deploy the robot to remove weeds using its linear actuator-driven mechanism. Measure the effectiveness of weed removal and assess any damage to surrounding crops.

Seed Sowing Experiment: Evaluate the robot's seed sowing precision and uniformity. Program the robot to sow seeds in designated plots within the field using the hog for drilling holes. Assess seed distribution patterns and germination rates in the treated plots compared to control plots.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The multipurpose use of agricultural robots has shown promising results in various aspects of farming, including planting, monitoring, harvesting, and weed control. These robots have demonstrated increased efficiency and precision compared to traditional farming methods. One key result is the optimization of resource usage, such as water and fertilizer, leading to improved crop yields and reduced environmental impact. Additionally, the use of agricultural robots has enabled farmers to manage larger areas of land more effectively, resulting in increased

Figure:2

Figure:3

II. CONCLUSIONS

The integration of IoT-enabled multipurpose agriculture robots marks a significant milestone in the journey towards a more efficient, sustainable, and resilient agricultural sector. By harnessing the power of data, connectivity, and automation, these robots empower farmers to overcome challenges and unlock new opportunities for growth and innovation in the ever-evolving agricultural landscape. As we continue to push the boundaries of technological innovation, the potential of these robots to revolutionize farming practices and feed the growing global population remains unparalleled.

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